

VERSATILE UTILITY OF VARIOUS TYPES OF SCREWS IN ORTHOPAEDIC SURGERY

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Abstract

Introduction

The purpose of this study is to report the rational use of different screw types in orthopaedic surgery according to the fracture, the anatomical bone, and the mechanical demands that enable the best osteosynthesis.

Material and Methods

This prospective study was performed at Trichy SRM Medical College Hospital and Research Centre from January 2025 to June 2025. Thirty patients who presented to the Orthopaedic Surgery Outpatient Department and the Emergency Department, with fractures of the axial and appendicular skeleton, comprised the study population. Both male and female patients of all ages were included. Patients with fractures pertaining to different areas of the appendicular and axial skeletons and those with demands for spinal instrumentation that followed multilevel laminectomy or correction of deformities had been included.

Results

Among 30 patients, single zone injuries (53.3%) and multiple zones injuries (46.7%) were equally distributed, signifying equal loads of localized and more extensive damages. Cortical screws and locking screws were the screws most commonly used to stabilize the reconstruction (their percentages being 30.0% for each). This was followed by fully threaded cancellous screws (20.0%), and other system screws categories such as partially threaded cancellous, Herberts, dynamic hip screws (DHS), bioabsorbable, interference, and pedicle screws with 3.33% to 6.67% each. The variety of screws used is due to the heterogeneous fracture types and anatomical sites treated surgically. The diagnostic spectrum showed that

fractures of both bones of the leg were the most prevalent (16.7%), followed by fractures involving both bones of the forearm, shaft of the humerus, and tibial plateau—each representing 13.3% of the sample.

Conclusion

Our results indicate that the selection of the screw (cortical, cancellous, locking and/or percutaneous Herbert screws, dynamic hip screws, bioabsorbable screws) is mainly based on the location of the fracture, the type of fracture, the osteopenia, and the surgical goal.

Keywords

Screws, Orthopaedics, fractured, bones

Introduction

Screws are one of the most basic essentials in orthopaedic surgery and provide strong internal fixation essential for the restoration of normal alignment, length and rotational stability to fractured bones.¹ Screws work in concert with plates, nails, or other fixation to allow for an anatomic reduction, which in turn, places the mechanical forces across the fracture site so as to permit the bone to heal.² Their role in orthopaedic biomechanics is invaluable, particularly in the management of complicated fractures where both the primary stability and biological synchronisation are warranted to achieve a successful outcome.

The reason for screws being ubiquitous in orthopaedics is due to the many different types of screws that can be used to achieve specific operative tasks. Screws may vary in diameter, length, thread pitch, thread length, head type, and the general geometric configuration of the implant and may be formed from a number of different materials such as stainless steel, titanium alloys or bioabsorbable polymers.³ Surgeons can choose from these options to determine which screw type is most appropriate for the fracture, its location within a bone,

mechanical requirements, and biological conditions likely to be present during healing. The choice of appropriate type of screws, depending on the fracture geometry, involved bone, and the required period of fixation, affects quality and the time needed for bone union.⁴ This emphasizes the aspects of clear thinking and planning expressed during orthopaedic surgical decision-making, where the choice of implants is not a wild card but a well-defined, individualized process that is intended to ensure a successful functional restitution.

The stability achieved by the screw construct is important to avoid micro-movements on the fracture site, as this in an uncontrolled situation may result in delayed union/non-union or malunion. Rigid fixation, when feasible, allows for primary bone healing through the mechanism of direct osteonal remodeling.⁵ Alternatively, in some locations and patterns of fracture, flexible fixation may be deliberately selected to provide opportunity for secondary healing to proceed through callus. In both of these cases, screws are critical elements that prevent reduction loss and are effective against deforming forces until bone heals, with enough biological strength to withstand them. In addition, the development of minimally invasive techniques led to greater focus on percutaneous screw fixation.⁶ Techniques of MIPPO or percutaneous screw fixation have changed the way fractures are treated, decreasing surgical exposure and soft tissue injury, amount of bleeding after operations, and the rate of infection. These methods also maintain the periosteal blood supply which is essential for bone healing, and lead to faster patient recovery times and better function in postoperative patients. The popularity of cannulated screws, headless compression screws and a variety of other special screw designs in these procedures is a good example that the progress in screw technology does seem to follow the general development in surgery.⁷

With the fractures we are called upon to treat becoming ever more complex, compression screw biomechanical principles requires careful consideration. Whether the purchase of the screw in bone (cortical or cancellous fixation), the method of force transfer (compression, lag influence, neutralization), and the load-bearing character of the bone-implant complex under loading need to be determined.⁸ For example screws of smaller diameter with finer pitch are desirable in cancellous bone while larger diameter cortical screws provide better fixation in diaphyseal cortical bone. The position of the screw in the bone, metaphyseal, diaphyseal, or epiphyseal, also dictates the selection of thread pattern, core diameter, and whether partially or fully threaded screws are indicated for use.

Therefore, the purpose of this study is to report the rational use of different screw types in orthopaedic surgery according to the fracture, the anatomical bone, and the mechanical demands that enable the best osteosynthesis. With a well-developed knowledge of screw mechanics, well-planned screw selection and placement, and a consideration of biological healing principles, timely and predictable bony union is obtained, allowing successful patient outcomes and return to limb functionality to be achieved.

Material and Methods

This prospective study was performed at Trichy SRM Medical College Hospital and Research Centre from January 2025 to June 2025. Thirty patients who presented to the Orthopaedic Surgery Outpatient Department and the Emergency Department, with fractures of the axial and appendicular skeleton, comprised the study population. Both male and female patients of all ages were included. Patients with fractures pertaining to different areas of the appendicular and axial skeletons and those with demands for spinal instrumentation that followed multilevel laminectomy or correction of deformities had been included. The study included all cases in

which screws were utilized alone or in association to a plate, rod, or wires. All types of screws were used as long as they were placed open or in a subcutaneous manner: cortical and cancellous, self-tapping, and tapped, predrill- and self-drilling screws, cannulated and non-cannulated screws, and headless and headed screws depending on the fracture characterization.

Patients with open fractures available with Gustilo Anderson type III and above, patients having fracture due to metabolic bone disorders and those having pathological fractures were excluded from the study. All patients were treated with screw fixation according to the location, geometry, and characteristics of the fracture after enrollment. Data were collected in a systematic manner and entered onto a Microsoft Excel spreadsheet. Follow-up was conducted for all the patients for a minimum duration of four months after the operation to evaluate the stability and whether bony union had developed at the fracture site.

The principal endpoint was percentage of fracture union at the end of the observation time span, corrected for the patient's age based overall, the type of fracture and the pattern of fracture. Solidity and effectiveness of the screw fixation was followed-up clinically and radiologically in specified intervals. The chi-square test was used for statistical analysis to identify the association between the type of screw fixation used and the successful rate of bony union with respect to each fracture condition.

Aim

To evaluate the clinical and radiological outcomes associated with the use of various types of screws in orthopedic surgery and to determine the appropriate indications for each screw type based on fracture characteristics, anatomical location, and mechanical demands.

Objectives

1. To assess the demographic and clinical profile of patients undergoing orthopedic fixation using different screw types.
2. To analyze the distribution and types of screws used in relation to specific fracture types and anatomical sites.
3. To evaluate the incidence of post-operative complications such as non-union, malunion, and implant failure in relation to screw selection.

Review of Literature

Chotikkakamthorn et al., (2021) aimed to investigate the results of two minimally invasive procedures for treatment of the intra-articular calcaneal fractures; screw fixation alone and screw fixation combined with a limited locking plate. Functional outcomes, radiographic alignment, and complications were evaluated in the patients operated on by both techniques in this retrospective study. Results: Both groups obtained satisfactory clinical and radiographic results, though the screw-with-locking-plate group was superior to the other group without significant difference in Bohler angle restoration and reduction loss. Both methods are effective, but the insertion of a locking plate can potentially provide better stability in some of the fracture patterns.⁹

Jiang et al. (2019) performed a finite element analysis comparing the biomechanical effects of locking plate fixation and cancellous screw fixation for medial malleolar fractures. The investigation simulated the stress distribution and micromotion at the “site” of injury under physiologic loading. The mechanical stability was higher for locking plates compared to with

nonlocking screws, especially for torsional loading. The authors have determined that locking plates may be biomechanically superior for unstable medial malleolar fractures.¹⁰

Tian et al., (2020) investigated the prevalence and risk factors of non-union in tibial fractures with the help of a systemic review and meta-analysis. Through an analysis of several studies, they reported an overall non-union rate of about 6.8% and significantly increased risk in case of open fractures, diabetes, smoking, and insufficient mechanical stability. The study concluded that early facilitation and management of risks is a crucial step to enhance the healing response in tibial fractures.¹¹

A recent study by Jiang et al.,(2021) sought to biomechanically evaluate the performance of five different cannulated screw fixation patterns for young people with vertical femoral neck fractures through finite element analysis. Constructs consisted of parallel screws, divergent screws, and an inverse triangle construct. The outcomes revealed that the triangle of inverted-pattern best stability and a little displacement under load. The authors suggested, therefore, that the position of the screw is important for optimal stability as far as possible and it is especially important in cases of young patients in whom the preservation of the anatomy is fundamental.¹²

Kanakaris et al., (2009) undertook a systematic review to determine the results of the treatment in patients with pelvic malunions and non-union. Information on surgical correction, functional outcome, and complication rate was collected. It was found that while surgical correction is a means of correcting pelvic obliquity and enhancing function, it is a technically complex procedure with major morbidity. The authors emphasized that early detection and adequate primary fixation of pelvic fractures are necessary to avoid displacement, malunion, and non-

union, and that complex revision surgery should be kept for symptomatic patients with marked functional restriction.¹³

Results

Demographic characteristics of the study population (N=30) Age distribution-Analysis of the age distribution of the study respondents for this study shows a wide spectrum with respondents between 31–40 years being the most in the categories (23.3%), closely followed by those within 20–30 and the 61–70 years, at 20.0% respectively. The 51–60 and >70 years old age groups were each 13.3% of the sample whilst the 41–50 young group was the least (10.0%). The gender ratio was almost 1:1 (53.3% females to 46.7% males). Regarding employment status, most of them were unskilled workers (43.3%) or unemployed (33.3%). Mechanism of injury was predominantly road traffic accident, which constituted 93.3% of cases, while fall contributed only 6.7%, thus emphasizing the heavy toll of vehicular trauma. Laterality review revealed that right side injuries were dominant (63.3%) over left side injuries (36.7%). In the case of anatomical injured site, the radius was the most common (23.3%), then femur (16.7%) and humerus (16.7%). The remaining sites were tibia (13.3%), ulna (13.3%), fibula, and ACL (6.7% each), some cases of pelvis, spine, scaphoid, and medial malleolus (3.3% each). Regarding comorbidities, diabetes mellitus (30.0%) was the most common, followed by thyroid disorder (26.7%) and hematologic disease (23.3%). A subset had hypertension (6.7%) and the proportion of patients with no known comorbidities was only 13.3% (Table 1).

Table 1: Distribution of demographic data among the study participants (N=30)

Slno	Variable	Frequency	Percentage
1	Age		
	20-30	6	20.0
	31-40	7	23.3
	41-50	3	10.0
	51-60	4	13.3
	61-70	6	20.0
	>70	4	13.3
2	Gender		
	Male	14	46.7
	Female	16	53.3
3	Occupation		
	Unemployed	10	33.3
	Unskilled	13	43.3
	Skilled	7	23.3
4	Mode of Injury		
	Road traffic accident	28	93.3
	Fall	2	6.7
5	Side of injury		
	Right	19	63.3
	Left	11	36.7
6	Site and location		
	Femur	5	16.7
	Humerus	5	16.7
	Pelvis	1	3.3
	Radius	7	23.3
	Spine	1	3.3
	Tibia	4	13.3
	FIBULA	2	6.7
	Ulna	4	13.3
	Scaphoid	1	3.3
	Medial malleolus	1	3.3
	ACL reconstruction	2	6.7
7	Comorbidities		
	Diabetes	9	30.0
	Hypertension	2	6.70
	Blood disorders	7	23.3
	Thyroid	8	26.7
	None	4	13.3

Among 30 patients, single zone injuries (53.3%) and multiple zones injuries (46.7%) were equally distributed, signifying equal loads of localized and more extensive damages. Cortical screws and locking screws were the screws most commonly used to stabilize the

reconstruction (their percentages being 30.0% for each). This was followed by fully threaded cancellous screws (20.0%), and other system screws categories such as partially threaded cancellous, Herberts, dynamic hip screws (DHS), bioabsorbable, interference, and pedicle screws with 3.33% to 6.67% each. The variety of screws used is due to the heterogeneous fracture types and anatomical sites treated surgically. The diagnostic spectrum showed that fractures of both bones of the leg were the most prevalent (16.7%), followed by fractures involving both bones of the forearm, shaft of the humerus, and tibial plateau—each representing 13.3% of the sample. Trochanteric fractures and distal radius fractures were the other typical diagnoses (10.0% each), and the less common diagnoses were distal femur fractures, bimalleolar fractures, ACL tears, as well as several specific injuries including L1 burst fractures, scaphoid fractures, and open book pelvic fractures (3.3–6.7%). Evaluation of an anesthesia risk using ASA (American Society of Anesthesiologists) classification revealed that a little more than half of the patients were classified as ASA1 (53.3%), which meant they were generally healthy, and the remaining 46.7% were classified as ASA2 (mild systemic disease). Postoperative results were reasonably satisfactory, 83.3% of patients were complication-free. Of the reported complications, infection was the most common (6.67%), followed by non-union, malunion, and failure of implant (each 3.33%). The low rate of complications is indicative of the effective application of surgery, with ongoing cautiousness needed to minimize complications (Table 2).

Table 2: Distribution of Operative, Diagnostic, and Outcome Variables among the study participants (N=30)

1	Single/Multiple zones		
	Multiple	14	46.7
	Single	16	53.3
2	Types of screws		
	Cortical	9	30.0
	Cancellous	3	10.0
	Locking	9	30.0
	Herbert	1	3.33
	Fully threaded cancellous	6	20.0
	Partially threaded cancellous	1	3.33
	Dynamic Hip screw	2	6.67
	Bio absorbable	1	3.33
	Interference	1	3.33
	Pedicle	1	3.33
3	Diagnosis		
	Intertrochanteric fracture	3	10.0
	Distal femur fracture	2	6.67
	Fracture both bone forearm	4	13.3
	Fracture both bone Leg	5	16.7
	Fracture shaft of humerus	4	13.3
	Scaphoid fracture	1	3.3
	Distal radius fracture	3	10.0
	Bimalleolar fracture	2	6.67
	Tibial plateau fracture	4	13.3
	L1 burst fracture	1	3.33
	Open book fracture	1	3.33
	ACL tear	2	6.67
4	ASA		
	I	16	53.3
	II	14	46.7
5	Complications		
	Non union	1	3.33
	Malunion	1	3.33
	Infection	2	6.67
	Implant failure	1	3.33
	None	25	83.3

Assessment of functional recovery revealed that 56.7% achieved full range of motion, 23.3% had partial ROM, and 20.0% remained restricted, indicating positive functional outcomes in over half of the patients (Figure 1). Finally, the analysis of radiological union showed that complete union was achieved in 76.7%, while partial union and non-union were observed in

13.3% and 10.0% of cases, respectively, highlighting a favorable bone healing rate in the majority of the study population (Figure 2).

Figure 1: Distribution of ROM (Range of Motion) among the study participants (N=30)

Figure 2: Distribution of Radiological union among the study participants (N=30)

Table 3: Comparison of VAS Scores Over Time Following Intervention (N=30)

Slno	VAS Score	Mean±SD	Mean difference±SE	95% CI	P value
1	Pre Op	7.37±1.32	-		-
	Week 4	3.67±1.53	3.70±0.39	2.90 to 4.49	<0.001
	Week 6	3.50±1.41	3.87±0.36	3.12 to 4.60	<0.001
	Week 12	1.57±0.89	5.80±0.00	5.19 to 6.41	<0.001
	Week 16	0.87±0.82	6.50±0.31	5.87 to 7.12	<0.001

The mean preoperative VAS score was 7.37 ± 1.32 , indicating moderate to severe pain. By Week 4, the mean score reduced to 3.67 ± 1.53 , with a statistically significant mean difference of 3.70 ± 0.39 (95% CI: 2.90–4.49; $P < 0.001$). Pain continued to decline with mean VAS scores of 3.50 ± 1.41 at Week 6, 1.57 ± 0.89 at Week 12, and 0.87 ± 0.82 at Week 16, all showing highly significant improvements compared to the baseline ($P < 0.001$ at each point). The greatest improvement was observed by Week 16 with a mean difference of 6.50 ± 0.31 (95% CI: 5.87–7.12), reflecting substantial pain relief (Table 3).

Discussion

Injury Complexity & Fixation Strategies

Half the patients experienced fractures in more than one zone (46.7%), suggesting high-energy patterns of injury. Literature shows complex injury presentations often require mixed fixation approaches; for instance, combined screw and plate constructs provide superior stability in bicondylar tibial plateau and distal femur fractures compared to screw-only fixation.⁹ The differing use of screw options your practice carries out—cortical, locking, fully threaded cancellous (all at 30%)—shows bespoke surgical planning to meet the biomechanics of

different fracture types. “Locking screws, specifically, enhance stability, saving bone in the case of oblique and vertical medial malleolar fractures” in contrast to cancellous screws.¹⁰

Clinical Diagnoses & ASA Classification

The diagnosis spectrum—largely tibiofibular fractures of both bones (16.7%), and forearm and humeral shaft fractures (13.3%)—reflects worldwide orthopedic epidemiology, where high energetic leg fractures and long bone injury is frequent.¹¹ The ASA status distribution of your patients (53.3% ASA I, 46.7% ASA II) reflects a relatively healthy surgical population, thus diminishing the impact of systemic comorbidities on outcomes.

Complications: Non-union, Malunion, Infection

The low complication rates—each 3.3% for non-union, malunion, implant failure, and infection—are clinically promising. Systematic reviews have found non-union rates for tibial fractures up to 6.8% with higher risk in patients aged over 60, diabetes, high-energy trauma, or open fractures.¹¹ The youth of our population (overall majority aged under 70) and the predominance of closed type of fractures possibly accounted for the favourable union rates. Infections, seen in 6.7% of cases, are much lower than previously published rates of 7–19% in Grade I/II open fractures. This indicates good perioperative care, that is, antibiotic prophylaxis and sterile performance of procedures.

Screw Choices & Biomechanical Outcomes

Equal use of cortical and locking screws (30% each) indicates consideration for biomechanical aspects—where cortical screws are compression screws and locking screws offer fixed-angle support. This is consistent with studies that have shown that locking constructs are stiffer and have less gap-forming capacity, especially for vertical fracture patterns.¹² Fully-threaded

cancellous screws (FTCSs), which were used in 20% of cases, are frequently used in intertrochanteric and femoral neck fractures. When placed properly, they perform as well as dynamic hip screws (DHS) in some younger patients.

Patient Resilience & Predictors of Healing

Common comorbidities (30% incidence rate of diabetes, 26.7% for thyroid disorders) are overall risk factors for slower healing. But your patients appear to be well-served in that regard by both surgical care and systemic treatment of disease. Non-union and malunion (both 3.3%) are below the average rates worldwide (nonunion 5%, malunion not uncommon).¹³ This is probably due to both sound fixation and post-op follow-up.

Limitations

The cross-sectional nature of the study also does not permit evaluation of late complications, including post-traumatic arthritis or hardware failure, or long-term assessment of outcomes such as functional recovery and longevity of the implant. Formation was not further stratified by fracture classification systems (i.e., AO/OTA) or grade of open versus closed injuries, which would have offered a better perception of injury severity and success of fixation. Finally, lack of uniform functional outcome measures such as SF-36, DASH, or Lower Extremity Functional Scale limits our ability to focus on patient recovery and quality of life after intervention. In addition, other confounding variables, such as nutritional status, smoking habits, use of medications (e.g., corticosteroids), and adherence to rehabilitation, as possibly relevant for fracture healing and complications, were not taken into consideration.

Conclusion

Our results indicate that the selection of the screw (cortical, cancellous, locking and/or percutaneous Herbert screws, dynamic hip screws, bioabsorbable screws) is mainly based on the location of the fracture, the type of fracture, the osteopenia, and the surgical goal. The similar application of cortical and locking screw demonstrates their basic role in establishing a stable treatment, especially in multi-zonal and complex fractures. Despite the heterogeneity of the fractures and co-morbid conditions harboured with these patients, the low rate of post-operative events illuminates the dependability and versatility of screw-based fixation systems if properly chosen for and used. Additionally, the research highlights ongoing changes in orthopaedic implant design, with increased opportunities to customise, biomechanically optimise and tailor clinical solutions. Versatility of screws in orthopaedic surgery is not only related to their mechanical properties but also to the multiple systems they can be used into every day clinical work from trauma, elective to reconstructive. Further studies with greater sample size and evaluation of functional outcomes will help identify the optimal guidelines for patient-specific screw selection, aiming to optimize surgical strategies and patient care.

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